

THREE COPIES AND THE TRUTH!

A RIFF ON PARSIMONIOUS PRESERVATION

FROM MUSIC CITY

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Abstract: “Three chords and the truth” has long described country music’s elegant simplicity and emotional resonance. Inspired by this ethos and Parsimonious Preservation, Vanderbilt University’s Special Collections and University Archives (SCUA) has developed a streamlined, scalable digital preservation ecosystem. It uses a minimal identifier schema based on the intellectual arrangement of archival finding aids from ArchivesSpace, integrated with AWS S3. The format-agnostic system supports everything from born-digital files to digitized 16th-century books. S3 file prefixes flow directly from the schema, enabling precise, index-free retrieval. The ArchivesSpace Digital Objects module ties everything together—linking descriptive metadata, digital surrogates, born-digital items, access and preservation copies, extended metadata, and eventually IIIF manifests. This approach shows how simplicity can drive sustainable, interoperable preservation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Preservation is a core aspect of the Vanderbilt University Libraries Strategic Plan [1]: one of the library’s four core strategies reads:

*“Engage locally, regionally and globally in creating access, disseminating knowledge and **preserving cultural memory.**”*

The sub goals of that strategy include, “Protect the legacy of the world’s cultural heritage by building and safeguarding collections with a focus on **preservation, access** and education;” and “Pursue effective and inclusive models for **digital** and material **preservation and stewardship** of collections.”¹

II. THE CHALLENGE

Vanderbilt University sees Digital Preservation as an institutional, socio-technical, and economic challenge that requires an institutional, socio-technical, and economic response. This perspective was highlighted in the Blue-Ribbon task force report from 2010 [2] and more recently by the Ithaka S+R team [3] who note:

“Rather than being seen as a standalone process, digital preservation should be approached as a suite of policies, services, workflows, processes, standards, and expertise required to keep information safe and accessible over time.”

¹ Our emphasis for this paper.

For their purposes Ithaka S+R look at a system as: *“people, technologies and structures designed to collect, process, store, distribute, and manage information.”*

Additionally in the Ithaka report, the authors observe that in practice *“Very little digital preservation activity is actually taking place”*. [3]

By grounding our Digital Preservation approach against the Vanderbilt University Libraries Strategic Plan [1], we aim to correct that situation in respect of the Digital Information Resources held by the Vanderbilt Libraries.

NOTE: We have adopted throughout the definition of Digital Preservation (and Digitization) from the Glossary [4] of the Digital Preservation Coalition’s (DPC) Digital Preservation Handbook.

III. ALTERNATE APPROACHES

In the last few years, many vendors [5] [6] [7] have proposed solutions that depend upon the implementation of a digital asset management system as the “guarantee” of digital preservation. Unfortunately, we perceive that these approaches are often monolithic, stove piped, and expensive. We feel they can easily result in product “lock in”, long term ongoing license costs, and impose on the institution a critical digital preservation dependence on the platform or system concerned.

Furthermore, case studies such as “Preservation Not Paralysis...” at University of Louisville [8] and “Bridging the Gap: Taking Practical Steps...” [9] have recently described lower cost practical approaches to tackle digital preservation that do not suffer from some of these issues. In a university setting, a case study of analyzing bit rot in Electronic Theses and Dissertations has also demonstrated the need to focus on the capture or intake of materials to initiate a simple preservation process [10] rather than the need for an immediate, all-encompassing preservation solution.

Our goal is to deliver digital preservation at Vanderbilt using an incremental, scalable, and manageable approach that exploits all the processes and systems we already have at our disposal and keeps costs low, rather than procuring a new, large, big-bang, unaffordable, and potentially unsustainable platform.

IV. OUR APPROACH

With all this in mind, we have applied approaches derived from the following concepts to address our Digital Preservation challenge:

- “Parsimonious Preservation” [11] [12]
- “Minimum Viable Preservation” [13] [14] [15].
- “Minimum Ingest Processing” [16] [17]
- “Preservation Not Paralysis” [8]
- “Bridging the Gap” [9]
- “Scalable Born Digital Ingest Workflows for Limited Resources” [18]

Drawing on the approach of Parsimonious Preservation and the later developments above, we carefully examined the properties of the “standard” technology offerings already supplied by our university and library technical infrastructure to establish how these could be used to achieve our preservation goals.

As a University Library, we have already elected to use cloud storage (as supplied by Amazon Web Services through the Vanderbilt University IT department). We discovered it is a straightforward matter to adjust the properties of such storage requiring the use of multiple regions and Write Once Read Many (WORM) settings. Very soon we intend to add an offline tape archive to hold “Custodial Copies” onsite [19]. This will allow us to achieve full 3-2-1 storage [20] – our “Three Copies” from the title.

In addition, we have a DACS-compliant finding aid platform in ArchivesSpace [21], and we have found that this provides excellent management, discovery, and access gateway functionality. This provides our oracle of truth!

In other words, we found that we have all the components we need to construct a single, coherent Digital Preservation Ecosystem from loosely coupled existing components, rather than seeking to purchase a commercial, monolithic digital preservation platform as a solution.

V. SYSTEM DESIGN PRINCIPLES

In tackling the potentially complex issues of digital preservation and in order to make the challenge tractable, we chose to adopt many of the principles of Systems Thinking [22]. As such the principles of Parsimony, Holism (i.e., addressing the

challenge holistically), Separation of Concerns, and Modularity pervade our approach. As noted in SEEBOK [22], *"The principles are not independent. They have synergies and tradeoffs."* and we have tried to take advantage of these.

In this respect, we have made one particular choice of note, and that is to outsource many of the challenges of digital access to third party hosting services JSTOR [23] and Aviaary [24]. This decision represents the interplay of the principles of Parsimony, Separation of Concerns, and Modularity together with Holism. We are confident that there is a beneficial systems simplification from separating the components addressing Preservation from the components providing Access.

Separately, we also believe that this produces a significant and intrinsic reduction in cybersecurity risk to our collections, by also applying the principle of minimization [25] from the secure systems design domain. Specifically, if there is no public access to the preservation system itself from the external environment, it is much easier to defend it and our most valuable information assets from external catastrophic cyber-attack.

VI. SERENDIPITOUS OPPORTUNITIES

Vanderbilt encountered a confluence of factors over a brief period that informed the need for our simple, extensible preservation model:

- Our Archival descriptions were only digitalized in 2018 to ArchivesSpace.
- Our Special Collections staffing nearly doubled from 9 to 17 over a 4-year period.
- Our Digitized holdings tripled over 3 years from 80tb to 273tb through one-time investments in outsourcing.
- We adopted AWS S3 as our primary storage in 2023.
- We introduced ArchivesSpace 4.0 in 2025 that includes a bulk archival object updater.
- VU had – and still has – no true all-in-one DAMS, just an amalgamation of digital platforms.

By the end of 2023, we had a pile of digital “stuff” and only concepts of a plan to do something with it.

Rather than seeing this as a problem we chose to see this as an opportunity; there was no legacy system with 20 years of technical debt to work

around, and no entrenched “Vanderbilt culture” cultivated by years of internal training/hiring cycles.

We moved forward by hiring new positions from 2023 to focus our work on digital materials, including a director with experience developing digital preservation capabilities. We formed a new section inside Special Collections and University Archives (SCUA) with an Associate Director of Digital Special Collections and hired a Curator for Born Digital materials for that section. We also elected as a strategic choice to join the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) as full members to contribute actively to the community and take advantage of the existing digital preservation knowledge base.

With a growing staff, supportive administration, and existing infrastructure in the IT and library system, we realized we were in a position to truly address the institutional, socio-technical, and economic challenge of digital preservation.

VII. ARCHIVESPACE FOR DESCRIPTION

Vanderbilt utilizes two primary systems for the maintenance of its digital holdings: ArchivesSpace, an open-source Archival Information Management System, that serves as the system of record for all metadata about the archival collections, university archives, rare books, artifacts, maps, digitized and born digital materials held in SCUA; and Amazon S3 buckets which contain the digital and digital surrogate files that make up the archive.

In ArchivesSpace there are two independent structures that describe the “accumulation” of the things in a collection. There is the physical arrangement of the storage of the things (described in terms of structures known as “Containers”), and a separate “intellectual” or “logical” structure that is used to capture the archival context (of creation) of the things. This intellectual structure is the implementation of the DACS (or ISAD(G)) standard of hierarchical archival description in ArchivesSpace.

A. Identifier Schema

At a foundational level, we have defined a schema that identifies every archival and digital object (an “ADO Identifier”) in ArchivesSpace. This schema is based on this hierarchical intellectual structure of the collections. It was inspired by the structure of the catalog references in the UK National Archives catalogue [26].

The schema allows for the construction of “human interpretable” identifiers – filenames, URLs and URIs that are clear, unambiguous, auto generatable, and processable. It enables the connections and distinctions between the original physical and born digital objects (or “things”), their descriptions, and other (digitized, transformed, or redacted) versions of the original objects, to be self-evident, supported, and discriminated. The aim of this approach is to simplify the accession, description, digitization, and preservation workflows in SCUA, and enable the storage of all digital materials to be consistently and coherently structured without the need to maintain separate indexing databases or metadata stores to identify digital materials and their locations.

B. Construction of ADO Identifiers

The SCUA Archival and Digital Object Identifier has a seven-part structure. Each part is separated by a “-” (hyphen) character and scales down from <Repository Code>-<Collection Identifier>-<Series>-<Sub-series>-<Sub-sub-series>-<Group>-<Item>. The various levels are padded with 2 or 4-digit numbers, depending on how many of each may appear alongside each other in the hierarchy of the finding aid.

The shortest valid ADO Identifier is one that refers to a collection:

spc-mss0123

At its longest, an identifier for an item could be:

spc-mss1234-s01-ss05-sss17-g0001-i0003

VIII. PRESERVATION ON AMAZON S3

A core benefit of implementing this ADO Identifier Standard is to enable our cloud storage on Amazon S3 to follow a parallel, logical structure for digital surrogates of physical Archival Objects and born-digital Archival Objects without the need for an independent “indexing” database.

S3 buckets have a flat, non-hierarchical file structure, which means there are no actual “directories” as such, as there would be on a traditional filesystem. However, objects in S3 buckets can be organized with prefixes, which give a similar effect to the directories or folders on a filesystem. We have defined these prefixes to follow the same ADO Identifier convention, meaning that our preservation system structure completely matches the intellectual

structure of our finding aids on ArchivesSpace. The location of the preservation copies – either as digitized copies of a particular archival object or processed born digital copies – can therefore be inferred without a separate lookup (although the location of preservation copies is nevertheless linked from a Digital Object).

The S3 bucket prefixes follow the outline in Fig. 1 below:

Fig. 1

Files may be deposited in the “directories” at any level in the hierarchy below repository-code and will relate to the archival object with that identifier. There is no restriction on the filetype of items stored.

The “born-digital” branch of the prefixes is used to capture and preserve the full original structure of born-digital accessions at the collection level, as uncompressed tar balls. Only once these have been further processed and described are the materials copied to the appropriate repository-code branch under the relevant ADO Identifiers. The original, context-capturing tar ball is always retained.

Just like the identifiers for archival and digital objects and the logical structure on S3, the filenames of digital surrogates follow the ADO Identifier structure. The file names of digital surrogates consist of the relevant archival object identifier, followed by an underscore (_), followed by a 4-digit zero-padded number (that indicates the sequence of images or pages) followed by an appropriate file name extension (e.g. “.tiff” or “.jpg”). A similar use of naming conventions and file extensions enables the storage

of redacted or compressed versions of the digital objects, as necessary. Furthermore, if we need to preserve other additional metadata associated with either the archival object (digital or physical), or a digital surrogate, we can use the same identifier schema to name the file containing the metadata and anchor it to the appropriate object using prefixes, naming conventions, and file extensions as above.

Putting this all together, the storage location for the preservation copy of, the digital surrogate of, the very first paper scanned from the very first folder of the James Lawson Collection [27] is:

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s3://ltp-scu/spc/mss0626/s01/g0001/spc-
mss0626-s01 -g0001_0001.tiff
```

IX. CONNECTING EVERYTHING

Accessed and managed via the *Digital Objects* Module of ArchivesSpace, Digital Objects (DOs) are the fundamental method by which the relationship of digitized and born-digital objects to their corresponding physical archival objects and/or their descriptions are recorded. The *Digital Objects* module is located within a repository in ArchivesSpace and sits alongside the *Resources* module which contains descriptions of collections and their archival objects. DOs themselves contain information describing the storage locations of preservation and access copies as well as how external links in the ArchivesSpace Public User Interface are displayed. This relationship is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2

It is important to note that in our case a single Digital Object is in one-to-one correspondence with an Archival Object. This one-to-one correspondence does not imply the number of digital files that make up Digital Object that may be used to depict or represent the corresponding Archival Object.

Continuing our earlier line of thought to abstract our thinking away from physical containers of

objects and focus on intellectual archival structures, fundamentally the Digital Object in our model does not concern itself with the “tangible representation/container” that are the individual files. Where that concatenated file-level information is needed, and will be recorded, is in something like a IIIF manifest. In that case, it would be linked as a *whole* from a digital object.

As with most everything in ArchivesSpace, the system-required fields for Digital Objects are simply a Title and an Identifier, both of which are directly analogous to the Archival Object linked to the Digital Object. From there, each institution that implements ArchivesSpace can use any number of optional DO fields.

Vanderbilt has found that the “File Versions” category contains everything needed to record all information on our digital and digitized holdings. For each representation of a Digital Object, you simply add another file version and define the version’s purpose through the “Use Statement” field. For Vanderbilt, we currently have 3 defined purposes: access copy, access copy thumbnail, and preservation copy. We plan to add IIIF manifest as a fourth in the near future. The fields for each of these are:

- File URI (which contains the ADO identifier)
- Use Statement
- Publish and X-link *Actuate* and *Show* attributes (to control how/if the URI appears to the public)
- File format *Name* and *Version* (based on PRONOM registry information)
- File size
- Checksum and Checksum Method
- Caption

At its core, completing these fields fulfills the core requirements for a minimum viable or parsimonious preservation system [13] [11].

X. PUTTING IT ALL IN TO PRACTICE

To put all of our plans into practice we needed some platforms on which to work with the digital materials, process and collate the relevant data and metadata, and actually preserve the digital files. As we are using existing IT systems in the form of

ArchivesSpace and S3 buckets, our existing laptops, servers, and cloud services provided some of what we needed. However, what we lacked were dedicated platforms to manage and process the digital surrogates and born digital files for ingest.

Three principal factors in considering what we needed from an “ingest” platform were cyber hygiene, simplicity, and cost. In the end we repurposed a number of old Windows workstations by fully reformatting their disks and installing Linux Mint, CLAM-AV, Sigfried and a number of other tools. This is not unlike the PAM recently created by Cambridge University Library [28].

Each of the machines is only connected to the internet and our university network for a minimum amount of time to allow software updates and AV updates to be downloaded prior to processing an accession. The machine is then disconnected or “air-gapped” during processing and only reconnected once ingest processing is complete for the accession to be uploaded to S3 and the metadata delivered to ArchivesSpace. All removable media is connected via hardware write blockers to ensure that the original files are not inadvertently altered by the ingest process. The purchase of the write blockers was the only new capital expense incurred in the delivery of our new ecosystem.

XI. OPERATIONAL SUCCESS

After SCUA established the use of ADO Identifiers, archivists soon began to create new and consistent born digital accession file names for uncompressed tar files holding born-digital accessions using the air-gapped Linux ingest machines. Our archivists also began retroactively adding ADO identifiers to processed and digitized collections on ArchivesSpace using the Component Unique Identifier field.

For born digital accessions, the naming convention for the tar files consists of the repository code, the year it was ingested to the repository, and a sequential number representing the order of arrival of collections in the year. Thus, for the 17th accession into the University Archives Repository (uar) in 2025, we used “uar-2025-017”. Using this convention, our archivists were able to upload the born digital accession tar files onto the system using the naming structure under the /born-digital branch of the prefixes as described in section VIII above.

In the case of retroactively adding ADOs to archival collections, one example included adding the identifiers to a post-custodial archival collection of digitized scrapbooks [29]. The identifiers were able to represent the three different archival series, pages or items in the scrapbook, and the front and back scanned pages that resulted in identifiers of the form spc-mss1117-s01-i0015. Using the schema, one archivist in our team developed a Python script to add identifiers to ArchivesSpace using the new bulk updater spreadsheet feature of ArchivesSpace 4.0.

In another specific instance, an archival collection that included a hard drive of a musician’s materials was first uploaded to AWS in the /born-digital section to achieve initial preservation. After the materials were organized, processed, and described on a finding aid, final preservation copies were then transferred to the S3 bucket alongside digitized preservation copies of paper holdings from the same collection in the same intellectual structure using the identifier schema [30]. Additional preservation metadata (checksums etc.) and compressed access copies (as appropriate) were stored in the same structure as described above. They will later be exported to the relevant access platforms from ArchivesSpace as our source of truth.

As a final example of using the digital object module on ArchivesSpace, a university archives record group with digitized audiotapes was linked to the URL locations of the S3 storage of the preservation copies and to the Aviary platform for access copies [31]. Using the file versions as noted earlier, the public version of the Aviary link serves as the system of record to discover the access copies as a public link, but the preservation copy file version on ArchivesSpace is not published and is securely available for staff use only.

For born digital accessions, the digital object module has been used to clarify via the use statement that it was a born-digital-record-master, included the preservation tar PRONOM information, and added the checksum generated during upload and transfer to AWS from the air-gapped ingest machine using the AWS CLI tools.

XII. CONCLUSION AND LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

As we have outlined above, Vanderbilt took the two systems it already used, ArchivesSpace and Amazon S3, and creatively used their existing functionalities to define a digital preservation

ecosystem. In the process, we did not need to create new plugins or bend systems into working in unintended ways. We simply used what was available to us and any other user.

We should also note that this is only a first step in implementing our goals. We are still actively adding ADO Identifiers to collections, migrating our digital backlog to our S3 Bucket while changing filenames, and linking Archival Objects to their corresponding Digital Objects. Our legacy of born digital materials is tracked in a digital asset register (using the DPC template [32]) until they are consolidated into AWS S3. Nevertheless, we are proud of the fact that no edge cases have “broken” our standards or approach yet, even if that happens in the future.

Beyond the work of adoption, Vanderbilt is looking at two future projects to build on the overall system design. First, we have a goal to fully implement IIIF in the near future. The exact design of the image API, manifest server, and viewer is yet to be determined, but we hope to automate adoption using the consistent standards defined here. The Digital Objects module will then hold this information on the locations of these IIIF artifacts. This will enrich our ability to provide interconnected access to digital resources within our own holdings and also to partner and collaborate with other institutions to provide still wider access.

Another challenge we expect to face is understanding future levels of access to born digital materials to manage copyright, PII, and researchers’ preferences. This may impact digital object description in ArchivesSpace. To build our manageable, scalable model for a few staff members, we are considering adding administrative and technical metadata to born digital collections that may exist on other fields in ArchivesSpace.

We believe our model represents an effective illustration of the ability for any institution, even with basic systems, to digitally preserve their content with a system that is scalable, manageable, incremental, and achievable with a small capital investment.

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